

RESEARCH PAPER

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A preliminary checklist of avifauna in Hullathi Section of Ranebennur Blackbuck Sanctuary, Haveri District, Karnataka, India

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Abstract

The Ranebennur wildlife sanctuary is located in Ranebennur Taluk of Haveri District, Karnataka. The sanctuary is declared on 17-6-1974 as per Government of Karnataka Notification No.AFD-58-PWL-74 with an area of 119 Sq.km (30,464 acres). This sanctuary mainly concerned with the conservation of Black bucks and Great Indian Bustard. Due to habitat loss GIB are not sighting since from 1998 and the sanctuary inhabits a wide variety of fauna and flora. The entire survey was comprehensively carried out by walking along the fixed paths for documentation of avifauna. Depending on the movement and occurrence, birds were classified as resident, resident migratory, local migratory, winter migratory and summer migratory depending on the frequency of sightings, birds were classified as: common, uncommon, rare and fairly common. The present study aims to estimate the avifaunal diversity in Hullathi section of Ranebennur wildlife sanctuary. The study revealed the occurrence of 104 species of birds in Hullathi section respectively. Among them Black-headed Ibis (*Threskiornis melanocephalus*), were listed in the near threatened category (IUCN, 2012). The result also showed that the agriculture land, wetland area and surrounding vegetation are favorable environmental conditions suitable for the migratory, resident as well as the threatened species of birds. These are protected under the provisions of schedule IV of Indian Wildlife Protection Act, 1972. The spotting of these threatened bird species highlights the importance of study area as an important feeding, staging and wintering ground for birds.

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Introduction

The planet earth embodies a variety of organisms including microbes like virus, bacteria and macro organisms viz, plants & animals which constitute the entire biodiversity. Avifaunal diversity is one of the most important biotic components for any type of ecosystem. (Dhindsa and Saini, 1994) and one of the most populous life forms on the planet, and that biodiversity leads to a richness of life and beauty. Birds are the potential umbrella group of species for biodiversity conservation (Branton and Richardson, 2011). It may be influenced by biogeography (Karr 1976). India being a mega diversity nation harbours more than 1,200 species of birds which amounts to 13% of the bird species of the world (9,600 species) (Ali & Ripely, 1987). The seasonal change in species diversity of birds occurs in forests is due to their foraging behavior (Robertson and Hackwell, 1995). However, the birds are affected due to natural or some human-induced disturbances Maurer *et al.* (1981), Wiens (1989), therefore, assessing the bird diversity of a habitat over time and space is important to know about the status of avian community.

The change in vegetation composition has a direct impact on birds in terms of their food, water and cover and its extent which consequently affect the diversity, abundance and distribution (Gregory *et al.*, 2003; Clawges *et al.*, 2008; Rajpar & Zakaria, 2011). The birds have always fascinated man for their exquisite coloration and courtship. They have their functional role in the ecosystem as potential pollinators and scavengers, indeed rightly called bioindicators (Dayananda, 2009). Birds are also the best monitors of environmental changes and have been used to evaluate the environment. Birds are excellent model organisms for understanding key changes in ecology, animal behavior, evolutionary biology and conservation (Urfi, 2011).

The changes in their population, behavior patterns and reproductive ability have most often been used to examine the long term effects of habitat fragmentation. Hence they are the good indicators of ecological status of any given ecosystem (Harisha and Hosetti, 2009).

Studies on the diversity of bird in a particular area are important for determining the health of the ecosystem (Wiens, 1989). Birds are very important wild creatures, as they help in pest control, pollination, cleaning the environment as scavenger as well as an important ecological indicator (Ali and Ripley, 1983).

Most of the birds are aesthetically significant to mankind and Bird-watching has become one of the most popular recreational activities around the world (Kronenberg, 2014; Ma *et al.*, 2013; Sekercioglu, 2002; White *et al.*, 2014), and has direct economic benefits as well as indirect benefits through numerous citizen science programs involving bird-watchers (Greenwood, 2007). Birds recording data plays a significant role in providing the baseline data regarding distribution of a particular species in a particular area and also offer useful information for identifying priority areas for conservation (Daniels *et al.*, 1991; Peterson *et al.*, 2000; Colin, 2000).

During the last few decades considerable studies on avifauna diversity from different parts of India is made available (Chandra and Singh 2004; Dodia & Dhadhal 2010; Joshi *et al.*, 2012 and Bagde, 2015). Studies on bird diversity can provide valuable information about monitoring of biodiversity and environment of the world at local, national and global level (Bird Life International, 2015). There are no reports on avifauna from this habitat; hence the hitherto study was conducted to prepare a checklist and also to identify the consequences of direct and indirect human interferences in the Hullathi section of Ranebennur Wildlife Sanctuary, Haveri District, Karnataka.

Materials and methods

Study area

Ranebennur blackbuck sanctuary is situated towards North-East of Pune, Bangalore National Highway No IV at Ranebennur North East of Ranebennur. It spreads in the arid and scrub zones of Ranebennur, Byadgi and Haveri district, where it comes under Tungabhadra River Valley Project. It is situated between 14°33' 00" to 14°46' 00" Latitude North.

75°30' 08" to 75°47' 21" Longitude East. The topography of the study area ranging from 531 to 762 above MSL and temperature varies from 25°C in winter to 40°C in the summer. March-April are the hottest months. Average rainfall is 600-620mm. The soil structure is "Gneisses" Shist and Granite of Archean era and Deccan trap rocks of tertiary era (Jagadish Chandra 1974). Since the area coming under Tungabhadra River Valley Project. The scrub forest is spread with a total area of 119Sq.Kms. An area of 14.87 Sq.kms in Hullathi Block has been notified as "CORE AREA" on 21-10-1982. The topography ranging from 488.62m-488.27m .It is situated between Longitude E-075°39' 58.24" and N-14°38' 58.05". Latitude E-075°39' 58.24" and N-14°38' 58.05".14.87 Sq. km in Hullathi. The Ranebennur wildlife sanctuary mainly concerned with the conservation of Blackbuck and Great Indian bustard and also it includes other important avifaunal diversity. The great Indian bustard is not sighted since 1998 due to habitat loss and poaching activities. The other fauna found in the sanctuary are Jackal, Fox, Wolves, Wild pigs, Porcupine and Hares etc.

Sampling methods

The checklist of avifauna of the Hullathi section are prepared based primarily on the field work conducted during October 2021- September 2022 across Ranebennur Blackbuck Sanctuary. A direct visual count with binoculars was done and wherever possible an actual count was taken by direct and point counting methods [5, 6] (Burnham *et al.*, 1980; Simpson 1949). A total of 12 visits (1 visit per month) were spent in the field observing bird diversity at most active period in the day that is ,morning from 6Am to 11 am and identified using Olympus binoculars (10x50) and field guides [7] of Grimmett *et*

al. (2001). The nomenclature followed here is Manakadan and Pittie (2001). The residential status on the movement and seasonality of occurrence the parameters are listed as; LM- Local migratory, WM- winter migratory and R- Resident depending on its movement and seasonality (Table-1). The relative frequency off the presence of the species has been assessed as very common (VC): seen during 80–100% of the field visits; common (C): found during 50–79% off the field visits; uncommon (UC): observed during 20–49% of the field visits; few (F): met less than 19% field visits and rare (R): found occasionally (Khan 1982). Classification of birds was made according to the book of Indian birds by Ali (2002). Photographs were clicked by digital camera (Canon). Fig.s and tables were prepared by using Microsoft Excel.

Results and discussion

During the investigation 104 different species of birds were recorded in the Hullathi section. Details such as common and scientific names, status and abundance of the avifauna are printed in (Table 1). The study revealed that occurrence of 104 species of birds belonging to 46 families and distributed in 17 orders (Table 1). The order Passeriformes dominated the list by 24 families with 52 species followed by Pelecaniformes with 3 families and 9 species, Coraciiformes with 3 families and 6 species, Piciformes and Bucerotiformes with 2 families and 2 species, Accipitriformes with each 1 family and 7 species, Galliformes with 1 family and 6 species, Cuculiformes and Columbiformes with 1 family and 4 species, Charadriiformes, Anseriformes, Strigiformes and Apodiformes with 1 family and 2 species. Caprimulgiformes, Falconiformes, Psittaciformes, and Podicipediformes with 1 family and 1 species each respectively.

Table 1. Systematic list of avifauna with their status and frequency in Hullathi section Ranebennur Blackbuck Sanctuary

SL	Common Name	Scientific Name	S	F
	ORDER:CUCULIFORMES			
	Family:Cuculidae			
1	Pied crested cuckoo	<i>Clamator jacobinus</i>	LM	C
2	Asian koel	<i>Eudynamys scolopaceus</i>	R	C
3	Greater Coucal	<i>Centropus sinensis</i>	R	C
4	Common hawk-cuckoo	<i>Hierococcyx varius</i>	R	Fc
	ORDER:COLUMBIFORMES			
	Family:Columbidae			

SL	Common Name	Scientific Name	S	F
5	Laughing dove	<i>Spilopelia senegalensis</i>	R	C
6	Ring dove	<i>Streptopelia capicola</i>	R	C
7	Blue Rock Pigeon	<i>Columba livia</i>	R	Uc
8	Eurasian collared dove	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	R	Fc
	ORDER:CAPRIMULGIFORMES			
	Family:Caprimulgidae			
9	Common Indian Nightjar	<i>Caprimulgus asiaticus</i>	R	C
	ORDER:ACCIPTRIFORMES			
	Family:Accipitridae			
10	Black –winged Kite	<i>Elanus caeruleus</i>	R	C
11	Black shouldered kite	<i>Elanus axillaris</i>	R	C
12	Brahminy kite	<i>Haliastur Indus</i>	LM	Rr
13	Shikra	<i>Accipiter badius</i>	R	Fc
14	Black kite	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	R	C
15	Hawk	<i>Buteo lineatus</i>	R	C
16	Crested serpent eagle	<i>Spilornis cheela</i>	R	Uc
	ORDER:FALCONIFORMES			
	Family:Falconidae			
17	Common Kestrel	<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>	WM	Rr
	ORDER:CHARADRIIFORMES			
	Family:Charadriidae			
18	Red-Wattled lapwing	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	R	C
19	Yellow- wattled lapwing	<i>Vanellus malabaricus</i>	RM	Fc
	ORDER:ANSERIFORMES			
	Family:Anatidae			
20	Spot -billed duck	<i>Anas poecilorhyncha</i>	R	Fc
21	Lesser whistling duck	<i>Dendrocygna javanica</i>	LM	Fc
	ORDER:PSITTACIFORMES			
	Family:Psittacidae			
22	Rose-ringed parakeet	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	R	C
	ORDER:PICIFORMES			
	Family:Megalaimidae			
23	Crimson –breasted barbet	<i>Megalaima haemacephala</i>	R	Fc
	Family:Picidae			
24	Lesser Golden backed woodpecker	<i>Dinopium benghalense</i>	R	C
	ORDER:STRIGIFORMES			
	Family:Strigidae			
25	Spotted owlet	<i>Athene brama</i>	R	C
26	Jungle owlet	<i>Glaucidium radiatum</i>	R	Fc
	ORDER:BUCEROTIFORMES			
	Family:Upupidae			
27	Hoopoe	<i>Upupa epops</i>	R	C
	Family:Bucerotidae			
28	Common grey hornbill	<i>Ocyrceros birostris</i>	WM	Uc
	ORDER:PASSERIFORMES			
	Family:Motacillidae			
29	Large pied wagtail	<i>Motacilla maderaspatensis</i>	R	C
30	Grey wagtail	<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	RM	Uc
31	White Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	WM	Rr
32	Yellow Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	WM	Rr
33	Paddy field pipit	<i>Anthus rufulus</i>	R	C
	Family:Hirundinidae			
34	Common or Barn swallow	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	LM	C
	Family:Dicruridae			
35	Black drongo	<i>Dicrurus macrocercus</i>	R	Fc
36	Ashy drongo	<i>Dicrurus leucophaeus</i>	R	Fc
37	White –bellied drongo	<i>Dicrurus caerulescens</i>	R	C
38	Bronzed drongo	<i>Dicrurus aeneus</i>	R	Uc
	Family:Sturnidae			
39	Rose coloured starling	<i>Pastor roseus</i>	RM	Rr
40	Black headed starling	<i>Sturnia pagodarum</i>	R	Uc
41	Indian Myna	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	R	Uc
42	Jungle Myna	<i>Acridotheres fuscus</i>	R	Fc
	Family:Corvidae			
43	House crow	<i>Corvus splendens</i>	R	C
44	Rufious Treepie	<i>Dendrocitta vagabunda</i>	R	C

SL	Common Name	Scientific Name	S	F
45	Blue jay Family: Ploceidae	<i>Cyanocitta cristata</i>	R	C
46	Baya weaver Family: Oriolidae	<i>Ploceus philippinus</i>	R	C
47	Eurasian golden oriole	<i>Oriolus oriolus</i>	R	C
48	Black-headed oriole Family: Paridae	<i>Oriolus larvatus</i>	R	C
49	Grey Tit Family: Campephagidae	<i>Parus major</i>	RM	C
50	Small Minivet	<i>Pericrocotus cinnamomeus</i>	R	C
51	Scarlet Minivet Family: Monarchidae	<i>Pericrocotus flammeus</i>	R	Uc
52	Paradise flycatcher Family: Cisticolidae	<i>Terpsiphone</i>	R	Uc
53	Common tailor bird	<i>Orthotomus sutorius</i>	R	C
54	Plain prinia	<i>Prinia inornata</i>	R	C
55	Ashy prinia Family: Phylloscopidae	<i>Prinia socialis</i>	R	C
56	Greenish Warbler Family: Muscicapidae	<i>Phylloscopus trochiloides</i>	WM	Rr
57	Magpie-robin	<i>Copsychus saularis</i>	R	Fc
58	Indian-robin	<i>Copsychus fulicatus</i>	R	Fc
59	Pied Bushchat	<i>Saxicola caprata</i>	R	Fc
60	Asian brown flycatcher	<i>Muscicapa dauurica</i>	R	Uc
61	Tickell's blue flycatcher Family: Pycnonotidae	<i>Cyornis tickelliae</i>	R	C
62	White Eared bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus leucotis</i>	R	C
63	Red-vented bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	R	C
64	Red-whiskered bulbul Family: Leiiothrichidae	<i>Pycnonotus jocosus</i>	R	C
65	Common babbler	<i>Turdoides caudate</i>	R	Fc
66	Jungle Babbler	<i>Turdoides striata</i>	R	C
67	White-headed babbler	<i>Turdoides leucocephala</i>	R	Fc
68	Large grey babbler Family: Nectariniidae	<i>Turdoides malcolmi</i>	R	Fc
69	Purple sunbird	<i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i>	R	Fc
70	Purple rumped sunbird Family: Estrildidae	<i>Leptocoma zeylonica</i>	R	Fc
71	Spotted-Munia	<i>Lonchura punctulata</i>	R	Fc
72	Black-headed munia Family: Dicaeidae	<i>Lonchura atricapilla</i>	R	C
73	Tickell's flowerpecker Family: Passeridae Subfamily: Passerinae	<i>Dicaeum erythrorhynchos</i>	R	Fc
74	House Sparrow Family: Laniidae	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	R	C
75	Rufous-backed shrike	<i>Lanius schach</i>	WM	Rr
76	Bay-backed shrike Family: Aegithinidae	<i>Lanius vittatus</i>	R	Uc
77	White-tailed iora or Marshall's iora Family: Timaliidae	<i>Aegithina nigrolutea</i>	R	C
78	Tawny-bellied babbler Family: Sylviidae	<i>Dumetia hyperythra</i>	R	Fc
79	Yellow-eyed babbler Family: Rhipiduridae	<i>Chrysomma sinense</i>	R	Fc
80	White-throated fantail ORDER: CORACIIFORMES Family: Coraciidae	<i>Rhipidura albicollis</i>	R	Fc
81	Indian roller Family: Meropidae	<i>Coracias benghalensis</i>	R	C
82	Blue tailed bee-eater	<i>Merops philippinus</i>	SM	Rr
83	Small green bee-eater Family: Alcedinidae Subfamily: Cerylinae	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	R	C
84	Pied kingfisher Subfamily: Alcedininae	<i>Ceryle rudis</i>	R	C

SL	Common Name	Scientific Name	S	F
85	Small blue kingfisher Subfamily:Halcyoninae	<i>Alcedo atthis</i>	R	C
86	White breasted kingfisher ORDER:GALLIFORMES Family:Phasianidae	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	R	Fc
87	Common quail	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i>	R	C
88	Grey partridge	<i>Perdix perdix</i>	R	C
89	Indian peafowl	<i>Pavo cristatus</i>	R	C
90	Jungle bush quail	<i>Perdicula asiatica</i>	R	C
91	Small button quail	<i>Turnix sylvaticus</i>	R	C
92	Grey francolin ORDER:PODICIPEDIFORMES Family:Podicipedidae	<i>Francolinus pondicerianus</i>	R	Fc
93	Little Grebe ORDER:PELECANIFORMES Family:Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	LM	C
94	Little cormorant Family:Ardeidae	<i>Microcarbo niger</i>	RM	C
95	Cattle egret	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	R	Fc
96	Median Egret	<i>Mesophoyx intermedia</i>	R	Fc
97	Little egret	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	R	Fc
98	Large Egret	<i>Casmerodius albus</i>	R	C
99	Pond heron	<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	R	Fc
100	Grey Heron Family:Threskiornithidae	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	WM	Uc
101	Black-headed ibis	<i>Threskiornis melanocephalus</i>	R,TS	C
102	Black ibis ORDER:APODIFORMES Family:Apodidae	<i>Pseudibis papillosa</i>	R	C
103	House swift	<i>Apus nipalensis</i>	RM	C
104	Crested tree swift	<i>Hemiprocne coronata</i>	R	C

S- Status of the birds observed as Resident (R), Winter Migratory (WM), Local Migratory (LM), and Resident Migratory (RM); F- Frequency Based on the occurrence of the birds: C-Common, Uc- Uncommon, Fc- Fairly common, Rr- Rare Threatened Species (TS).

The residential status of avifauna in Hullathi is 82% resident, 5% local migratory, 7% winter migratory, 5% resident migratory, and 1% summer migratory. Frequency of occurrence of avifauna is 52% common, 29% fairly common, 11% uncommon, 8% rare species and also we found near threatened species like Black-headed ibis (*Threskiornis melanocephalus*) in the area. The distribution and occurrence of avifauna appeared to be associated with the vegetation patterns of the area, which is of great significance. The forest is of scrub most of the area covered with grassland and diversity of plant species is more, 5% of Eucalyptus trees are there in this section and 3 to 4 water ponds are present respectively. So we found maximum number of birds in Hullathi area (Fig. 1, 2, 3, 4). Most of the water birds recorded from the study area were found to utilize different habitats extensively for foraging, roosting and sometimes nesting on the emergent and fringed vegetation. The rich diversity of the avifauna documented during the

present study may be because of availability of varied sources of feed as well as foraging habitats. This habitat by supporting different food sources like fruits, grass feed, croplands and invertebrates (Harisha *et al*, 2011). This indicates that the habitat is more suitable and supportive to all the visitor as well as resident birds by providing immense food and space to breed.

Fig. 1. Residential status of Avifauna in Hullathi section of Ranebennur wildlife Sanctuary.

Fig. 2. Frequency of occurrence of Avifauna in Hullathi section of Ranebennur wildlife sanctuary.

Fig. 3. Number of Families in Order.

Fig. 4. Number of Species in Order.

The record of 104 bird species in the entire sanctuary indicates suitable habitat quality and diversity in the hitherto scrub forest. It is evident that variation in vegetation structure influenced species distribution (Mac Arthur *et al.*, 1962; Karr & Roth, 1971; Pearman 2002) within a habitat. Hence effective steps should be taken for the protection of Threatened species such as Black-headed Ibis (*Threskiornis melanocephalus*) were listed under near threatened category (IUCN, 2012) and are protected under the schedule IV of

Indian Wildlife Protection Act, 1972 [Arora K (2002)]. Conservation of birds and vegetation to protect the avian diversity of the area can provide more protection to threatened bird species of India. The spotting of these threatened bird species highlights the importance of study for important feeding, staging and wintering ground activities of birds.

Conclusion

The spotting of these threatened bird species highlights the importance of study area as an important feeding, staging and wintering ground for birds. It is the need of the hour to monitor these areas systematically in the rapidly changing environment with a focused study on status, distribution and conservation of the avifauna of the region. Great Indian bustard is one of the rare birds in the world and is not sighting since 1998 due to habitat loss and habitat modification. GIB is also small number found in states like Rajasthan, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh, and Karnataka and it is the state birds of Rajasthan. Due to destruction of habitat it is now limited to a few areas, like Rajasthan and Gujarat where it is protected on religious sentiments. The sanctuary is fully covered by Eucalyptus hybrid plantation and these trees show allelopathic effects; they release compounds which inhibit other plants species from growing nearby. It dries out the sub soil water consequently, lowers the water table and also it adversely affects the soil moisture regime native vegetation is practically expletive, other than the sanctuary and it is covered with *Acacia Arabica*, *Acacia latronum*, *Acacia leucophloea*, *Prosopis juliflora*, *Hardwickia binata*, *Albizzia amara*, *Albizzia lebbek*, *Dodonia viscose*, *Cassia articulata*, *Carissa carandus*, *Lantana camara*, *Cassia fistuala*, *Datura innoxia* etc.

The distribution and occurrence of avifauna appeared to be associated with the vegetation patterns of the area. Difference was noted in diversity and species richness in Hullathi section. Due to the habitat i.e. availability of food, water, climatic conditions are favorable to birds in this area and surrounding vegetation comparatively uneven favorable for avian fauna.

So many varieties of birds around the sanctuary and those will feed on *Ficus* species, fruits, insects, nectar from flowers of the trees and there are many streams, ponds are present around the sanctuary. Especially, Department should do the Programme to removal of eucalyptus plantation stage by stage and planting of fruit trees, and also there is a pressure from villagers around the sanctuary harm breeding behavior of birds and might result in significant habitat alteration. In addition, increase in due to cattle grazing, human habitation, cutting of the forest areas etc might lead to further depletion in the bird diversity over a period of time. To conserve fauna and flora further strategies, laws should be implementing by the department and also expand the resources to the needs of future generations.

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